

Isolated Swallowing Disorders in a Patient with Medial Medullary Infarction : A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Swallowing disorders are common in brainstem strokes but rarely occur in isolation. Medial medullary infarction (MMI) typically presents with multiple neurological deficits, making isolated dysphagia an uncommon presentation.

We report a 48-year-old man admitted 2 hours after symptom onset with sudden severe dysphagia, without other neurological symptoms (NIHSS = 0). Examination revealed an absent gag reflex on the left side. Brain MRI showed an acute infarction of the left medial medulla, with diffusion restriction and no FLAIR abnormality, consistent with hyperacute ischemia. Thrombolysis was not performed after risk–benefit assessment. The patient was treated with antiplatelet therapy and underwent swallowing rehabilitation, with complete recovery after two weeks.

This case highlights that isolated dysphagia may be the sole manifestation of MMI. Despite a low NIHSS score, such presentations may be functionally disabling, requiring early recognition and appropriate management.

Keyword: Medial medullary infarction; Brainstem stroke; Swallowing disorder; Young adult stroke

INTRODUCTION

Swallowing disorders (SD) is a frequent problem in the acute phase of stroke, increasing both mortality rates and hospitalization time.^[1-2] Research indicates that up to 78% of patients with medial medullary infarction (MMI) suffer from swallowing disorders. Delayed swallowing reflex is described as a typical symptom of dysphagia in MMI, whereas decreased laryngeal elevation is mostly attributed to patients with lateral medullary infarction.^[4]

We report a rare case of medial medullary infarction presenting with isolated dysphagia due to delayed swallowing reflex, without any other neurological deficits.

CASE REPORT

A 48-year-old man with a history of hypertension and sleep apnea was admitted to the emergency room 2 hours after the sudden onset severe dysphagia. He was unable to eat, drink, or handle saliva; he denied vertigo, dizziness, nausea, unsteady gait, numbness, or weakness.

The Modified Rankin Scale (mRS) and National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale (NIHSS) scores on admission were both zero (0).

Neurological examination revealed equal and reactive pupils; extraocular movements were full. There was no ptosis, and the corneal reflex was present bilaterally. There was no spontaneous or gaze nystagmus, saccadic pursuit, or ocular dysmetria. Facial symmetry was preserved, with no signs of weakness. The gag reflex was absent on the left side, with drooping of the soft palate on the left. The tongue protruded in the midline with good lateral movements on command. The remainder of the cranial nerve examination was normal.

Motor strength was preserved. There were no sensory deficits to touch, pain, temperature, vibration, or position sense. Deep tendon reflexes were normal, and there were no pathological reflexes. Coordination of the extremities was intact. Gait was not ataxic.

Figure: Brain MRI obtained 2 hours after symptom onset demonstrating an acute infarction of the left medial medulla. (A) Diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI) shows a focal hyperintense lesion. (B) FLAIR sequence remains isointense. (C) The ADC map demonstrates a corresponding hypointensity, confirming restricted diffusion. The **DWI–FLAIR mismatch** is consistent with hyperacute ischemia.

The stroke was attributed to atherosclerotic disease. The patient was started on aspirin and atorvastatin for secondary prevention. Intravenous thrombolysis was not administered after multidisciplinary evaluation, given the isolated presentation and the risk–benefit assessment.

From admission, the patient was fed via a nasogastric tube. With intensive swallowing rehabilitation, including physical and speech therapy, oral intake was progressively resumed, and the patient regained swallowing function after two weeks.

DISCUSSION

The medullary swallowing center, located in the brainstem, is the second most significant swallowing control area, following the cortex and subcortex. This center comprises the nucleus ambiguus, nucleus tractus solitarius, and adjacent reticular formations, all of which are responsible for governing the swallowing reflex. Damage to the medullary swallowing center can lead to a loss of inhibition over the pharyngeal phase of swallowing, causing it to last longer.^[3]

The delayed swallowing reflex observed in our patient can be explained by the disruption of corticobulbar pathways projecting onto the nucleus ambiguus, which plays a central role in the motor execution of swallowing. Beyond this primary mechanism, the close anatomical proximity of other swallowing-relevant medullary structures — namely the central pattern generators of the reticular formation, the hypoglossal nuclei, and the nucleus tractus solitarius — means that even a small infarction in this territory can significantly impair swallowing coordination.^[4,5]

Isolated swallowing disorder in brainstem stroke is extremely rare, as the lesion must be strictly confined to the swallowing center without extension to adjacent structures.

Our patient presented with a small infarction of the left dorsomedial medulla oblongata, which was revealed by isolated dysphagia and absence of gag reflex on the left side. The peculiarity of our case lies in the absence of other neurological deficits typically associated with medullary infarction, such as limb weakness, sensory disturbances, cerebellar signs, or cranial nerve involvement, including dysphonia, dysarthria, facial palsy, facial sensory change, tongue weakness, beyond those related to swallowing.

According to current guidelines, intravenous thrombolysis is recommended in patients with disabling symptoms, even with a low NIHSS score (0–5).^[7] Although isolated, dysphagia may be considered disabling due to the risk of aspiration, malnutrition, and infection. In our case, the decision to perform thrombolysis was challenging, and treatment was not administered based on an individualized risk–benefit assessment.

The medial medullary territory is mainly nourished by the paramedian twigs of the perforating arteries. According to some authors, the most common mechanism of the MMIs is small vessel disease of the latter twigs^[6], which is consistent with our case.

Research suggests that effective post-stroke SD management requires a multidisciplinary approach incorporating physical therapy, speech therapy, acupuncture, and other emerging medical and industrial techniques.^[3]

CONCLUSION

This case report describes the critical role of the medullary swallowing center in the pathophysiology of SD and demonstrates that medial medullary infarction may exceptionally present as an isolated swallowing disorder.

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